

DISCUSSION ON THE FAILURE MECHANISM OF RC BEAMS STRENGTHENED IN SHEAR BY EXTERNALLY BONDED CFRP SHEETS

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SUMMARY: The technique of strengthening or repairing reinforced concrete (RC) structures with externally bonded steel plates or composite sheets have been successfully applied in civil engineering. The RC structure is **often** strengthened in flexure. In this work, the authors study the failure mechanism of the shear strengthening of RC beams. Five types of beam with different dimension of strengthening composite **fibre** reinforced plastic (**CFRP**) sheets were used. . The appearance of the initial cracks, the crack propagation in the structure up to the ruin was monitored and discussed In particular, for one of the strengthened RC beams, the failure mode and the failure mechanism are fully analysed. The experimental results show that the crack modes were greatly influenced by the dimension and the position of the strengthened CFRP sheet. The crack began always in flexure. The first cracks were found to be in concrete at the tensile region and at the beam **centre**. The appearance of the cracks in the RC beam extremity is very late.

KEYWORDS: strengthening, beam, carbon **fibres**, crack, bending, failure

INTRODUCTION

The external bonded composite materials are used more and more in the strengthening and repairing of existing reinforced concrete (RC) structures, especially in bridge and building structures. The principal reasons can be that the composite materials have high tensile strength, corrosion resistance, and high fatigue strength and are particularly lightweight. The strengthening and repairing technique of RC structures by composite plates externally bonded to the tension face has been studied by researchers and many bridges have successfully strengthened in flexure [1-7]. However, as the structure tensile strength increases, the probability of the structure failure in shear is high And the shear failure of RC structures is dangerous due to their brittle nature and unexpected failure.

In this present paper, the reinforced concrete beam has been strengthened with externally bonded carbon **fibre** reinforced plastic (CFRP) sheets. One beam is strengthened in flexure

and four others are strengthened in flexure and in shear. The failures of the strengthened RC beam have been noted in three modes in general: failure mode in flexure, in shear and in hybrid flexure/shear. For the beam strengthened only in flexure, the failure is often precipitated by the horizontal tearing of concrete cover below the level of internal reinforcement. After the strengthening of beam in shear, the failure mode is different. The failure process of the beams strengthened in shear were carefully monitored and discussed. For the strengthened beam the ultimate strength can have a significant increase in comparison with the normal beam. However the experimental results indicated that the beam strengthened in flexure and in shear did not have any advantages, in ultimate strength, in comparison with the beam strengthened in flexure.

RC BEAMS WITH BONDED CFRP

The RC beams were designed in the four-point bending system; all beams have been strengthened by externally bonded carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) in flexure (Fig.1). Then they have also been strengthened on the flanks of the beam by CFRP with different dimensions. The beam dimension used in this study is 1350-mm long, 200-mm wide, and 130 mm deep. Shear reinforcement consists of 6-mm diameter stirrups, placed at 150-mm spacing. The steel reinforcement has a yield stress of 550 MPa. The concrete material properties were obtained from four uniaxial tests on cylindrical specimens 320-mm long, 160-mm diameter. The measured compressive strength, shear strength and elastic modulus were 37 MPa, 4.3 MPa and 35 GPa, respectively. The CFRP sheet used in flexure in experimental program is 900-mm long, 100-mm wide and 0.5-mm thick CFRP sheets and the sheet consists of unidirectional carbon fibres at a volume fraction of about 75 percent bonded together with an epoxy matrix. Uniaxial testing of the sheets gave an average elastic modulus of 120 GPa and a strain in failure of 0.008. The value of the adhesive elastic modulus was found to be 3 GPa and the tensile strength was measured to be 31 MPa.

Fig. 1 Reinforced concrete beam strengthened by externally bonded CFRP sheets

Five different shear strengthening beams were tested. Beam A had only strengthening CFRP sheets in flexure. Beam B had been strengthened by CFRP sheets in bending and in shear on the flanks below the level of internal rebars. Beam C had strengthening CFRP sheets in bending and in shear on the flanks of the beam where the shear force exists. Beam D had strengthening CFRP sheets in bending and in shear on the flanks of the beam below the mid-height. Beam E had strengthening CFRP sheets in bending and in shear on the flanks of the concrete beam below the level of internal reinforcement upper rebar.

FAILURE MODES AND ANALYSIS

RC beams strengthened externally by CFRP sheets loaded in bending have been noted to fail in a number of possible ways. The failure modes may be summarised as follow [8]:

1. The **flexural** dominant failures are initiated by yielding of the internal reinforcement. The **flexural** failures may be also initiated by concrete compressive **flexural** stresses without yielding of the internal reinforcement. The CFRP sheet bonded to the concrete bottom may fracture or buckle due to tensile stresses, resulting in **flexural** failure. The RC beams may fail due to normal stresses, resulting in **flexural** failure.
2. Concrete shear failure in the form of diagonal cracking may occur if the shearing strength of the beam is inadequate to develop its **flexural** capacity. The shear failures are greatly influenced by the ratio of shear span to beam depth.
3. A hybrid failure is initiated by the horizontal tearing of concrete cover below the level of internal reinforcement.
4. The concrete may crush in the **compressive** zone of the beam if the concrete strength is weak or the presence of web reinforcement is such that the beam shear strength and the **flexural** capacity increase remarkably.
5. The bond, on the tensile face, at the CFRP-concrete interface may fail causing debonding. Debonding may occur if the epoxy adhesive strength is weak or the substrate surfaces are not well prepared on which there may be the dust and loose particles so that the assemblage quality of the concrete and CFRP sheet is not assured. In general, debonding at the concrete-CFRP interface is unlikely to occur due to the very low magnitude of the shear stresses (relative to the shear strength of high-quality epoxy adhesive). The shear strength of good epoxy adhesive is often several times higher than that of concrete, and shear connectors can eliminate the possibility of bond failure completely.
6. The CFRP sheets at the flanks of the beam may buckle or fracture due to shear stresses. The sheets may also tear due to the twist of beam in loading.

In general, debonding at the concrete-CFRP interface is believed to not have taken place if adequate precautions are taken in the preparation of the substrate surface and the epoxy adhesive used has the sufficient strength. The concrete failure in compression is unlikely to occur due to its strength and this failure mode can be avoided in the beam design. The hybrid failure of the horizontal tearing of the concrete cover below the level of internal reinforcement is **often** observed. However, the shear failure takes place without warning and is highly brittle.

Fig. 2 shows the beam cracks **after** the failure. The ruin of the strengthened beam is recorded by the horizontal tearing of the concrete cover below the level of internal reinforcement. For beam A, the cracks exist in three regions: the concrete compressive region, the shearing region and the bending region. The beam B **after** failure shows that there is a great concentration of stress in the shearing region. The cracked lateral composite sheets are due to the shearing stress. However, the phenomenon of the beam C after failure is **different**. The shearing region is greatly strengthened so that the stress distribution is changed and a number of cracks appear in the bending region. The strength capacity in shear is **greatly** reinforced. In increasing the lateral strengthened surface, the appearance of the number of cracks lessens.

There are only a few cracks observed in beam E. The cracks are not observed in the bending zone.

The high performance of the adhesive and the quality of the epoxy adhesive on the strengthening sheets was **confirmed**, the connection between the concrete and the sheet was not damaged. However the concrete was deteriorated in certain zones.

Beam A after the failure

Beam B after the failure

Beam C after the failure

Beam D after failure

Beam E after the failure

Fig. 2: Beam cracks after the failure

STRAIN

The number and the position of the strain gauges were shown in fig.3. Strain gauges G_0 and G_1 were stuck on the steel rebar surface of the tension zone. Strain gauge G_2 was stuck on the concrete surface in the compressed zone. Strain gauges G_3 and G_4 were stuck on the surface of strengthened CFRP sheet in flexure. Strain gauges G_5, G_6, G_7, G_9 and G_{11} were stuck on the surface of strengthened CFRP sheet in shear.

Fig. 3: Position of the strain gauges

The strains obtained for the sheet by gauge G_3 are shown in Fig.4. The curves of Fig.4 show that there are three parts for all the beams. The first part considers that the beam is in the elastic domain. The beam is loaded from 0 up to the critical load where the first cracks appear. The second part is a zone where the strain increases quickly while the load applied remains stable. This part may be considered as the number of the cracks increasing in the tensile zone of the concrete. While the stresses loosen due to the cracks increasing, the loading does not step up. When the concrete in the tensile zone doesn't response anymore, the sheets and the steel bars entirely suffer the loading. The load-strain response continued almost linearly. However, the stiffness of the beam was less great.

Fig.4. Load versus strain on the bottom of the CFRP sheets (G_3)

This applied load varies according to the strengthening beam dimension and its position at the flanks. The beam without strengthening CFRP sheet in shearing (specimen beam A) is more deformable compared to the beams strengthened in shear. In increasing the strengthening surface at the flank, the beam is less deformable.

The stiffness is almost identical for beam C and beam E. The stiffness of beam D is highest. This is probably due to the strengthening sheet position at the flanks of the beam. In fact, for beam D, there are no strengthening sheets at the flanks between the points of the load applied. In this case, the part in the beam centre of steel bars resists more than that of the beam strengthened at the centre flanks. This result shows the effect of the strengthening sheets in the flanks of the beam. In the meantime the beam strengthened in the whole flanks is not necessary, because the strengthened effect is not obvious in comparison to the beam strengthened in the flanks at half high. This is seen with the help of the results obtained by the gauge G_3 .

The load-strain curves obtained by the gauge G_4 for five beams are presented in Fig.5. Beams A, B, C and E are seen to have the same stiffness over the service load range, but beam A doesn't have the second part of the curve. Beam A is cracked as soon as the appearance of the first cracks in the beam end.

The crack load is up to about 93 kN. In this zone, the composite sheet deforms very little. At the ultimate load, the maximal strain is only 130 micros. The stiffness is almost stable. Beam D is seen to be less stiff than the other beams in this zone. But after the change of the stiffness at a load of about 50 kN, beam D gradually loses the **stiffness** up to the end. The load-strain curve for beam B resembles that of beam A, the stiffness suddenly changes and the strain quickly increases **after** the load of 80 kN. The mechanic behaviour is different for five the beams. Beams A and B, which are not strengthened or strengthened little in shear, are brittle and elastic. Beams C, D and E have a great plastic **part**. They are deformable, especially for beam D. It is important to note that the effect of strengthening in shear is remarkably present in this zone.

Fig.5: Load - strain curves for the strain gauge G_4

FAILURE MECHANISM

Failure modes are denoted as flexure, flexure/shear and shear. The flexure/shear failure is a hybrid mode of failure where there is yielding of internal reinforcement and external CFRP sheet prior to failure, but failure is precipitated by the horizontal tearing of concrete cover below the level of internal reinforcement. Shear failure essentially describes a premature, highly brittle failure in the form of shearing-off the concrete along the level of the internal reinforcement with no evidence of debonding of interface prior to failure. In addition, there is no yielding of either the main reinforcement or the CFRP sheet.

To better understand the crack mechanism and the crack propagation of the beam strengthened in shear undergone a flexion with four-point, beam E was selected and 10 gauges were stuck on the beam (fig.3). Strain gauges G_5 , G_6 , G_7 , G_9 and G_{11} were stuck on the composite plate lateral surface in the direction longitudinal. The distance between two strain gauges was 10 cm.

Figure 6 represents the results obtained by the strain gauges G_6 , G_9 , G_7 , G_{11} and G_5 . These strain gauges give local micro-strains. As the applied load increases, the great strain begins to appear from the beam centre towards the beam extremity G_5 .

Fig.6: Load - strain curves of beam E

It is obvious that the first cracks appear in the RC beam medium in the tensile zone. Then they are propagated towards the beam extremity. The appearance of the first cracks due to the bending moment with a load of approximately 30 kN corresponding to a strain of $0.219 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (Table 1). When the load increases from 30 kN to 47 kN, the gauge G_9 records the appearance of the cracks in this part. At this point, the strain, which corresponds to a load of 47 kN, is approximately $0.226 \cdot 10^{-3}$. The appearance of the cracks in the part, where the shear force exists, is at a critical load of 60 kN corresponding to a strain of $0.224 \cdot 10^{-3}$. This load value of 58 kN is two times greater than the load that provokes the first cracks. It means that the cracks due to the shear force appear later. When the cracks appear at the CFRP sheet end, the load has a value of 100 kN and this value corresponds to a strain of $0.146 \cdot 10^{-3}$. Table 1 shows the successive progress on the cracks appearance in the longitudinal direction. It is also obvious that as soon as the cracks appear, the strain increases suddenly. Up to the ultimate load, the

strain of the lateral CFRP sheet on the beam extremity is always in the lower value. The maximal value does not exceed $0.042 \cdot 10^{-3}$.

Table 1: Cracks propagation state

Load (kN)	Strain ($\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$)				
	G ₅ (10cm)	G ₁₁ (20cm)	G ₇ (30cm)	G ₉ (40cm)	G ₆ (50cm)
30	19	50	13	88	<u>219</u>
47	30	89	54	<u>226</u>	1308
60	31	153	<u>224</u>	1063	1721
74	37	<u>391</u>	727	1572	2090
100	<u>42</u>	2068	1828	2367	2721

Fig.7. Load - strain curves of beam E

The load-strain curves measured by the gauges (Fig.7) show that the appearance of the first cracks is in concrete due to the **flexion**. The cracks were found in the beam centre and in the tensile zone. The three gauges G₀, G₄ and G₆ indicated the same results. In the case of the same applied load, the composite sheets (curves G₃ and G₆) deformed more than the steel rebars (curve G₀) in concrete. The deformation speed of the sheet located at the bottom was more rapid than that of the lateral sheet. It is probable that the two gauges were not in the same layer of the beam, resulting in the different bending moment. However, **after** the cracks propagated up to a certain height in the vertical direction, the two curves (G₃ and G₆) were almost identical except at the ultimate load. The appearance of the cracks, which were always in concrete, was gradual towards the beam end (Fig.7). In the same loading, the strain value in the centre was always great and then it is successively less to the beam extremity. The load-strain curves obtained by the gauges G₁, G₄ and G₅ show well the low strains before the load of 84 kN. It can be observed that it is the strain gauge G₁, located at the steel rebar face,

which recorded the cracks at first. It is believed that the load of 84 kN indicated the appearance of the cracks in the steel bar-concrete interface. After this value, the strain in the steel bar increased very quickly. The concentration of stress was more and more high. And up to a moment, the beam was cracked causing the normal stress. The form of the rupture was the separation between the steel bar and the concrete layer below the steel bar level. This process of rupture is not inversive. But it is interesting to remark that gauge G_5 recorded the feeble strain. At the ultimate load, the strain is only $0.042 \cdot 10^{-3}$. This value is five times less than that of the first cracks measured by gauge G_6 . It may mean that the strengthening at the flanks of the beam for this zone, above the level of the steel bar, is not necessary.

CONCLUSION

For a reinforced concrete beam, the failure modes are generally denoted as flexure, **flexure/shear** and shear. For the purpose of the strengthening of the RC beam with externally bonded CFRP sheets, the beam can be strengthened in flexure, in shear or in **flexure/shear**. The results of tests performed in this study indicate that stiffness increases in increasing the CFRP sheet area at the flanks. However, this type of increasing has a limit. The results measured by the strain gauges showed ,that the strengthened composite sheet at the lateral faces delayed the appearance of the first cracks in concrete.

The crack modes were greatly influenced by the dimension and the position of the strengthened CFRP sheet. The crack modes' depend strongly on the strengthened way. The results obtained by the experimental test show that the occurrence of the first cracks is always provoked by the bending moment for all beams. For beam A without strengthening CFRP sheets in shear, the failure mode is associated with the sudden horizontal tearing of the concrete cover along the level reinforcement. With certain dimensions of the **CFRP** sheets, the first **flexural** cracks can be stopped by the sheet bonded on the flank. However, the strengthened beam becomes highly brittle and the failure in shear takes place without warning. The experimental curves give that the cracking pattern in shear failure of RC beams strengthened in flexure and in shear is not identical to the corresponding case in normal RC beams and RC beams only strengthened in flexure.

After the first cracks, the load was redistributed. The composite sheets and the steel bars in the tension region suffered the applied load. In the case there is no strengthening in flexure at the beam centre, the rupture will be caused by the bending moment. In case the sheet was not strengthened enough, it is possible to have the composite sheet cracked. The composite sheet in lateral faces plays a great role is stopping the crack propagation. To strengthen the reinforced concrete beam in shear, it is necessary at the same time to strengthen the beam in flexure or to assure the strength in flexure. The appearance of the cracks in the beam extremity is very late.

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